

Anaesthetic Considerations in a Patient of Wilson's Disease Undergoing Upper Limb Orthopaedic Surgery

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ABSTRACT

Wilson's disease or Progressive Hepatolenticular Degeneration is a genetic disorder of copper metabolism primarily affecting liver and brain, therefore anaesthetic management of this disease could be challenging due to altered drug metabolism and physiological response. Here we are presenting the successful anaesthetic management of a case of Wilson's disease undergoing upper limb orthopedic surgery.

Keywords: Wilson's disease, Copper metabolism, Supraclavicular brachial plexus block, Ultrasound

INTRODUCTION

Wilson's disease (WD) is a rare (0.5 in 100000) inherited disorder of copper metabolism primarily affecting brain and liver^[1]. This condition is due to the mutation of ATP7B encoding ceruloplasmin protein primarily involved in copper transport and excretion, which leads to excessive copper deposition in various tissues. Presenting symptoms of WD can range from neurologic abnormalities (dysarthria, rigidity, tremor, involuntary movements), psychiatric illness to liver dysfunction, hematologic dysfunction etc^[1,2,3,6]. Diagnosis of Wilson's disease includes low levels of serum copper and serum ceruloplasmin, increased urinary excretion of copper^[4,6]. The gold standard for diagnosis is measurement of hepatic copper content by percutaneous needle biopsy. Nowadays effective management of WD is available with regular follow up and copper chelating agents and absorption blockers^[1]. Anaesthetic management of patients with WD are met with many challenges because of pre-existing organ dysfunction, drug interactions, altered drug metabolism and altered physiology.

CASE REPORT

A 24 year old male (BMI-19kg/m²) with fracture of distal end of radius (right) (**Figure 1**) after a fall came for Pre-anaesthetic checkup. He was planned for open reduction and internal fixation using 7 hole recon plates with screws.

On examination he was found to have low mood, slurring of speech, jerky involuntary movement on all four limbs and tremors. Routine preoperative investigations revealed.

Hemoglobin:8.4 g/dl, Total leucocyte count:9000/cu.mm, Platelet count 174000/cu.mm, Blood urea:42mg/dl, Serum creatinine :1.1mg/dl international normalized ratio (INR):0.96 and Total bilirubin: 2.5mg/dl, Aspartate aminotransferase: 82U/L, Alanine aminotransferase :64U/L, Electrocardiogram- sinus tachycardia, Chest X-ray-Normal study. He was referred to neurology (neuropsychiatric symptoms, deranged liver function test, mild anaemia) for further evaluation.

Ophthalmologic examination revealed Kayser-Fleisher (KF) rings and sunflower cataract (**Figure 2**) on slit lamp examination.

Urinary copper level in 24hrs is 108µg, Serum ceruloplasmin levels :8mg/dl, Fibro scan of liver : F1 mild fibrosis, MRI Brain : Areas of bilateral thalamic, peri-ventricular & upper brain hyperintensities, Features are suggestive of metabolic conditions likely-Wilson's disease, Endoscopy: Normal study, Ultrasonography whole abdomen : Grade 1 fatty liver, 2D Echocardiography: Good biventricular systolic function with LVEF-64% and Trivial Tricuspid regurgitation. Patient was referred back for Pre anaesthetic checkup for further evaluation. He was diagnosed with Wilson's disease after previous referral to neurology. Since then (20days) patient was put on Tab. Penicillamine 250mg Thrice daily, Tab Zinc sulphate 200mg Thrice daily, Tab Trihexyphenidyl 2mg Thrice daily, Tab Tetrabenazine 25mg thrice daily, Tab Levetiracetam 250mg Twice daily. On examination patient had fine tremors and dysarthria but there was symptomatic improvement from last evaluation. The case was posted for surgery after taking suggestions regarding peri operative management from neuromedicine point of view.

Patient was premedicated with Tab Alprazolam 0.25mg on the night before. After taking informed consent a venous access was obtained and standard monitoring was done. Under all aseptic precautions, inferior, middle and superior trunk of brachial plexus were located around subclavian artery with pleura and 1st rib inferiorly using ultrasonography. After infiltrating with local anaesthetic (inj. Lignocaine 1ml), USG guided 20 gauge needle was introduced under ultrasound guidance and supraclavicular Brachial plexus block (Figure 3) was given using of inj. levobupivacaine 0.5% , 6ml in each inferior, middle and superior truck. After confirming adequate sensory and motor block in supraclavicular brachial plexus territory, surgery was started and completed in 90mins. Intraoperatively the patient remained hemodynamically stable and he was transfused with 700ml of crystalloid with blood loss of 250ml. His visual analogue score was < 3 at 14 hours post- operative and patient's satisfaction score was high (Lickert scale 5). Patient was later shifted to post operative care unit for 24hr observation.

Figure1. Xray of forearm (antero-posterior and Lateral view) showing radius and ulna, with fracture at distal end of radius

Figure 2. Slit lamp examination showing 1. Kayser Fleischer ring- golden brown pigmented deposition of copper around the cornea 2. Sunflower cataract- sunflower shaped cataract seen at the centre of cornea

Figure 3. Supraclavicular Block- Ultrasonographic picture showing A. Subclavian Artery, B. Needle, C. Pulmonary pleura lying inferior to subclavian artery, D. Middle trunk of BP, E. Inferior trunk of BP, F. Superior trunk of B

DISCUSSION

Anaesthetic management of patients with WD requires optimal planning for peri operative monitoring as it can cause further worsening of the condition.

In case of general anaesthesia (GA), care to be taken while selecting drugs since many induction and inhalational agents can cause hypotension leading to decreased hepatic blood flow, which could precipitate liver failure [2]. Because of pre-existing hepatic dysfunction, inhalational and intravenous agents can have accentuated effects and prolonged action due to reduced protein binding and slow metabolism [1,2,4,5]. Induction agents like ketamine and etomidate should be avoided as they can precipitate seizures [1]. Prolonged duration of action of muscle relaxants due to lower metabolism and chronic use of penicillamine can make airway management difficult [1,2,4,5].

Succinylcholine should also be avoided in patients with polyneuropathy and myopathy as it can cause hyperkalemia [1]. Post operatively patient can have respiratory failure due to prolonged action of muscle relaxants and there can also be exaggeration of neuropsychiatric illness (delirium and agitation) due to poor pain control.

Because of the various complications associated GA, regional anaesthesia (RA) can be a safely administered sole anaesthetic

technique over GA ^[1]. RA can be administered safely as the peripheral motor function remain relatively intact, but any pre-existing neuromuscular weakness should be documented ^[1]. RA has also decreased the use of analgesics which have hepatic metabolism and minimised the risk of neuropsychiatric deterioration due to opioids ^[2,3]. RA is also associated with less haemodynamic instability, which is necessary to prevent exacerbation of hepatic and neuropsychiatric dysfunction.

CONCLUSION

Thorough pre anaesthetic checkups are necessary for the effective perioperative management of the patients as many of them can present with undiagnosed medical conditions. Patients of Wilson's disease should undergo extensive multisystem evaluation before planning for anaesthesia due to the preexisting multiorgan dysfunction. Regional anaesthesia is always preferred over general anaesthesia as it has relatively less risk of exacerbation of neuropsychiatric and liver dysfunction.

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